

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		M	N	OI
Pd(DTTH) ₂	Orange red	21.83 (21.96)	23.27 (23.12)	—
Pt(DTTH) ₂	Yellowish	34.42 (34.04)	19.32 (19.54)	—
Ru(DTTH) ₂	Black	21.73 (21.51)	23.10 (23.37)	—
Rh(DTTH) ₂ .1.5H ₂ O	Red	14.81	24.07	—
Pd(DTTH) ₂ .Cl ₂	Reddish brown	19.27 (19.08)	19.98 (20.09)	12.56 (12.73)
Pt(DTTH) ₂ .Cl ₂	Yellowish brown	30.70 (30.19)	17.13 (17.33)	10.95 (10.98)
Pd(DTT)Py ₂	Red	23.62 (23.51)	18.47 (18.56)	—
Pt(DTT)Py ₂	Yellow	36.41 (36.05)	15.25 (15.52)	—
Ru(DTT)Py ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dark green	25.01 (25.01)	17.12 (17.32)	—
Rh ₂ (DTT) ₂ .Py ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dull red	21.52 (21.35)	20.12 (20.33)	—

* Py=Pyridine.

110° indicating that pyridine is also bonded to the metal atom. All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic which confirms the presence of oxidation state of +3 for Rh and +2 for Ru, Pd and Pt. The diamagnetism of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes suggests their four-coordinated square-planar structure. The diamagnetism of Ru^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes suggest their octahedral geometry.

The complex Pd(DTTH)₂ exhibits a medium band at 17 860 cm⁻¹ assignable to ¹A_{1g}→³A_{2g} transition in square planar field⁴. The rhodium complex Rh(DTTH)₂.1.5H₂O displays a strong band near 22 200 cm⁻¹ due to charge transfer and, a shoulder near 19 230 cm⁻¹ due to ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{2g} transition in distorted octahedral field^{5,6}. A broad and weak band at 16 930 cm⁻¹ in the reflectance spectra of Ru(DTT)Py₂.2H₂O can be assigned to ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{2g} transition in approximately octahedral field. Other complexes do not display distinct band in the visible region. The Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes M(DTTH)₂ and M(DTTH)₂.Cl₂ do not display distinct band but display a broad absorption below near 23 500 cm⁻¹ attributable to charge transfer absorption as the band is located at lower energy than the expected ligand field transition^{4,7}.

The ligand displays SH stretch at 2 460 cm⁻¹ which disappears in almost all the complexes indicating the coordination of the ligand through deprotonated (SH) sulphur. The broad NH stretch of the ligand (2 900–3 090 cm⁻¹) disappears in the complexes containing the dianionic ligand but retains as distinct band at 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹ in the complexes containing monoanionic as well neutral ligand indicating that one of the thioamide NH is not involved in bonding in the complexes with monoanion or neutral ligand while involved in coordination in complexes with dianionic ligand. The hydrated complexes display a broad band at 3 400 cm⁻¹ attributed from ν_{OH} of water molecule.

The δ_{NH} (1 491 cm⁻¹) and τ_{NH} (787 cm⁻¹) bands also disappear in the complexes with dianionic ligand, while these are raised to higher frequency in the complexes with neutral and monoanionic ligand and observed at 1 522±8 and 792±10 cm⁻¹, respectively. In finger print and far-infrared region, the ligand displays a number of bands due to thioamide groups, ring skeletal vibrations and ring deformation vibrations⁸; but in the complexes with dianionic ligand most of them disappear and are observed as broad and medium bands indicating that both the thioamide groups are involved in coordination and the complexes M(DTT)Py₂ (M=Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}), Ru(DTT)Py₂.2H₂O and Rh₂(DTT)₂.Py₂.2H₂O are polymeric. The thioamide bands I (1 491 and 1 470 cm⁻¹) of the ligand are raised to higher frequency and merge together with ν_{C=N} of the ligand and observed as a broad band at 1 505–1 530 cm⁻¹. The thioamide band⁹ IV (917 cm⁻¹) shifted to lower frequency and appeared at 805±15 cm⁻¹ indicating the involvement of the thioamide group. The pyridine adduct complexes display a medium band at 1 610 (CN) and 1 010± cm⁻¹ (pyridine ring breathing mode) suggesting the coordination of pyridine nitrogen in complexes¹⁰.

References

1. P. D. SINGH, N. K. JHA and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, 42, 282.
2. J. SANDSTROM, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1961, 15, 1295.
3. S. J. LAPLACA and J. A. IBERS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 778.
4. W. ROY MASON and H. B. GRAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 5221.
5. J. SCHERZER, P. PHILLIPS, L. OLAPP and J. EDWARDS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 847.
6. H. H. SCHMIDTKE, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1965, 339, 103; B. T. HEATON and H. SHAW, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 589.
7. H. B. GRAY and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 85, 260.
8. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1967.
9. N. F. CURTIS and Y. M. CURTIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 804.
10. N. S. GILL, R. H. NUTTALL, D. E. SCAIFFE and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 18, 79.

Synthesis and Characterisation of Mercury(II) Complexes of some Aromatic Amine N-Oxides

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THIS paper reports the synthesis and characterisation of Hg^{II} complexes with 5,6-benzoquinoline-N-oxide (Benzqno) (I) and 2-ethoxycarbonyl-

aminopyridine-*N*-oxide (Ecapo) (2).

The coordinating abilities of these ligands with other metal ions have been reported earlier¹.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligands Benzqno and Ecapo were prepared by *N*-oxidation of 5,6-benzoquinoline and 2-aminopyridine², respectively.

$Hg(\text{Benzqno})_2X_2$ ($X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{SCN}, \text{NO}_3$): A mixture of an ethanolic (20 ml) solution of Benzqno (2 mmol) and an ethanolic solution (10 ml) of the respective mercury(II) salt (1 mmol) was refluxed for 1 h. On cooling overnight, the resulting crystalline compounds were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure (~70%).

$Hg(\text{Ecapo})X_2$ ($X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{SCN}, \text{NO}_3$): A mixture of equimolar amounts of mercury(II) salt solution (1 mmol in 10 ml ethanol) and Ecapo solution (1 mmol in 10 ml ethanol) were refluxed for ~1 h. The resulting solid complexes were isolated as above (~60%).

Analytical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
	Hg	Anion	N
$Hg(\text{Benzqno})_2\text{Cl}_2$	30.12 (30.30)	10.52 (10.73)	4.11 (4.23)
$Hg(\text{Benzqno})_2\text{Br}_2$	26.52 (26.71)	21.13 (21.31)	3.62 (3.73)
$Hg(\text{Benzqno})_2\text{I}_2$	23.54 (23.74)	29.72 (30.07)	3.20 (3.31)
$Hg(\text{Benzqno})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	28.10 (28.37)	16.14 (16.41)	7.80 (7.92)
$Hg(\text{Benzqno})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	27.80 (28.06)	—	7.71 (7.83)
$Hg(\text{Ecapo})\text{Cl}_2$	44.52 (44.80)	15.62 (15.86)	6.14 (6.25)
$Hg(\text{Ecapo})\text{Br}_2$	37.11 (37.37)	29.59 (29.82)	5.10 (5.21)
$Hg(\text{Ecapo})\text{I}_2$	31.56 (31.80)	39.98 (40.28)	4.34 (4.44)
$Hg(\text{Ecapo})(\text{SCN})_2$	40.50 (40.71)	23.36 (23.55)	11.25 (11.37)
$Hg(\text{Ecapo})(\text{NO}_3)_2$	39.74 (40.05)	—	11.06 (11.18)

The ir spectra (KBr and nujol) of the complexes were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophoto-

meter in the range 4 000–200 cm^{-1} . The molar conductances of 10^{-3} *M* solutions in PhNO_2 were measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge at room temperature. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in PhNO_2 .

Results and Discussion

Lower molar conductances of the complexes in PhNO_2 indicate their non-electrolytic nature, which is further supported by molecular weight data in the same solvent.

A decrease in the $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ band at 1 240–1 220 cm^{-1} of the ligand on complexation is attributed to coordination of the oxygen atom of the *N*-oxide to the metal due to a decrease in π -character of N–O bonding. The N–O bending vibration at 840 cm^{-1} (ligand) appeared almost at the same position in the complexes. The C–H out-of-plane deformation modes underwent slight positive shift on complexation due to decrease in electron density on the aromatic ring.

Ecapo showed extra IV bands due to urethane group ($\text{RNHCOO}_2\text{H}_2$). The amide I band in Ecapo appearing at 1 730 cm^{-1} shifted to lower wave number in the complexes, indicating coordination through the carbonyl oxygen atom. The ν_{NH} band in free Ecapo appearing at 3 200 and 3 120 cm^{-1} remained unaffected in the complexes. This rules out the possibility of coordination through imine nitrogen atom. The bands at 450–430 cm^{-1} were assigned to Hg–O vibrations.

The ν_{HgCl} vibration³ were observed at 255–210 cm^{-1} . The thiocyanato complexes showed bands at ca. 2 100 (CN), 720 (CS) and 415 cm^{-1} (NCS), which clearly indicate coordinated S-bonded thiocyanato groups⁴. The nitrate complexes showed a monodentate bonding mode of nitrate in the complexes⁵.

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References

1. R. K. AGARWAL and S. C. RASTOGI, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1983, 62, 379; M. SRIVASTAVA, A. K. SRIVASTAVA and R. K. AGARWAL, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1984, 58, 393; R. K. AGARWAL, J. R. OHOPRA and S. C. RASTOGI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 154; R. K. AGARWAL and S. K. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 597; R. K. AGARWAL, H. K. RAWAT and G. SINGH, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal Org. Chem.*, 1986, 16, 801; R. K. AGARWAL and S. K. GUPTA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1986, 98, 313.
2. A. R. KATRITZKY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2064.
3. J. R. FERRARO, C. CRISTALLINI and G. ROCK, *Ric. Sci.*, 1968, 38, 433.
4. J. L. BURMEISTER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 205; 1968, 3, 225.
5. C. C. ADDISON and B. M. GATEHOUSE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 613; F. H. JARDINE, A. G. VOHRA and F. J. YOUNG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 2911.